

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

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“TEACHING ENGLISH FOR PROFESSIONAL PURPOSES AT THE TERTIARY LEVEL: BENEFITS FOR STUDENTS' CAREERS”

Excellent English language skills open doors to global opportunities. English for Professional Purposes (EPP) primary objective of teaching at the university level is to prepare students ready for the real world. EPP as integrated in various programs concentrate on the language and communication skills required in professional contexts, including meeting participation, report writing, and presentation.

English as a universal language is used as the business language to establish global connections and because of the presence of technology opportunities and employability's has no borders at all which give wider horizons for students who will be applying for a job after college.

Developing practical abilities that are immediately applicable to their chosen careers is one of the primary benefits of EPP. Student taking teacher education are taught in utilizing the language for teaching and learning preparation that includes lesson planning and class demonstrations. Business related courses students are honed to speak the language in mock interviews and presentations of their business studies. Courses in line with technology utilizes English in their technical writing classes, programming and coding descriptions. All these initiatives in teaching English are directly useful in their future careers.

In conclusion, English for Professional Purposes gives students the tools they need to succeed in the workplace and have more career options that are not only limited inside the country but globally.